

Strategic Considerations for Lead Pollution Control in Kanpur City

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This paper deals with the lead pollution control strategies in the perspective of ambient pollution profile for the year 1991-92. Lead is monitored in ambient air for Kanpur at three locations : industrial, commercial and residential, deploying atomic absorption spectrophotometry. The ambient lead level for a typical inland industrial/commercial city is discussed here based on seasonal variations, monthly averages, annual means and source profile. The results project that the gasoline based autoexhaust is the predominant source for lead pollution in Kanpur city.

In the last decade, there has been an awareness of the problem of lead in air in relation to human health due to automobile exhaust emission. Though the average per capita consumption of petrol in the country is quite low, the quantum of its usage in metropolitan cities is quite high^{1,2}. In terms of vehicular growth, two-wheelers have recorded an yearly average increase of 16.6% followed by cars (6.9%) and buses (5.7%)³. India has become the world's largest market for two-wheelers, edging Japan to the second place. In 1989, two wheelers' sales in India totalled 17.50 lakhs as against 16.88 lakhs in Japan. The country has a vibrant market and the industry can hope to sustain a minimum growth rate of 10 percent in the coming years, crossing 27 lakhs by 1994-95.

Lead and its compounds are associated with fine particulate matter in ambient air which are of prime importance from human-health point of view. These fine particles penetrate even up to alveoli resulting ultimate absorption/adsorption of lead in the blood stream and deposition on trachea⁴. The persistence of these particles in the atmosphere is governed by the fineness of particle size where they can either undergo chemical reaction or are transported over long distances from their sources to pristine areas of the environment^{5,6}. It is documented that the elevated concentrations of fine dust in Indian urban cities is a common phenomena attributable mostly to the fuel combustion including automobile engines and background natural dust due to arid climatic condition prevalent during major period of the year.

In urban atmosphere, lead originating from automobile exhaust is considered to be a significant contributor to total atmosphere lead^{7,8}. It is observed that lead content of airborne dust decreases exponentially with distance from the road⁹. The population living in industrial areas receive relatively higher concentrations of lead^{10,11}. Exposure to ambient lead pollution has now become an almost inescapable issue of urban life throughout India¹²⁻¹⁵. As a consequence, the health and well-being of urban residents will further deteriorate with high ambient lead pollution. Planning for sustainable development in the context of management of lead pollution thus requires a systematic scientific data base on lead level profiles. With this backdrop, this communication elaborates the monitoring scenario and control strategies for lead pollution in Kanpur city.

Kanpur is the largest industrial city in the State of Uttar Pradesh. It is an inland city on the bank of the river Ganga with hectic industrial and commercial activities. Kanpur is passing through a rapid phase of urbanisation. As per 1991 census record, the total population of Kanpur is about 2418485. The number of both petrol and diesel driven vehicles has shot up phenomenally by 190-200 times and industries have multiplied five to six fold. Its repercussions are evident on natural resources : air, water, land etc. The common pollutants emitted into the atmosphere from industrial emissions, conventional domestic fuel burning, and autoexhausts are suspended particulate matter (SPM), and toxic lead metal as aerosol both in organic form as tetraethyl/methyl lead and inorganic lead aerosol form invariably adsorbed on fine inhalable particles (<P10).

Results and Discussion

The inhalation of fine dust causes a variety of respiratory, allergic and skin ailments depending on size ranges duration of exposure in the ambient air. In view of above, three sampling locations were selected in Kanpur city to assess the impact of activities which are shown in Fig. 1.

Particulate matter : It is documented that the ambient air at Kanpur is enriched with high concentration of suspended particulate matter (SPM). Further analysis of SPM on size fractionation indicates that the respirable particulate matter (RPM) which is <10 μm size, is also at a substantially high profile. It is reported that an average concentration of RPM in Kanpur city remains well above promulgated standard for industrial, commercial and residential areas¹⁶. The result showed that the concentration of RPM ranged 44-341 and 50-388 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in 1991 and 1992 respectively. Incidences of high concentrations of 978 and 2274 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ were recorded at industrial and commercial sites in 1991 and 1992 respectively. Though RSPM concentration were high under the impact of major contribution from autoexhaust, the contributions from small-scale industrial activities, domestic sources and incidental contributions from background natural sources can not be ruled out. However, the fact remains that the major portion of ambient lead and other toxic metals are concentrated in the fine size carbon soot particles exhausted from automobile engines.

Fig. 1. Location of AAQ stations.

Airborne lead concentrations :

Airborne lead is contributed mainly by automobiles activities and industrial sources. The environmental issues pose a significant challenge to lead producing industries. Monthly lead concentrations in Kanpur city ranged $0.7-1.7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, maximum being recorded in the month of May (Fig. 2). The CPCB lead standards are exceeded in 7 months of the year indicating population exposure to high lead concentrations.

Fig. 2. Monthly variation of lead levels in Kanpur City.

The seasonal variation of lead profile (Fig. 3) indicates that Kanpur city experiences high lead concentration in the winter months. This can be attributed to the meteorological phenomena of low mixing heights due to temperature inversion during winter season. In Kanpur, due to erratic and low rains during monsoon of 1991-92, the lead concentration are on higher side, while in summer due to large mixing heights, the lead pollution is comparatively at low profile.

The activitywise analyses of lead pollution indicate that commercial zone recorded higher lead levels followed by

Fig. 3. Seasonal variation of lead levels in Kanpur city.

Fig. 4. Activity zonewise lead pollution levels in Kanpur city.

residential confirming the source apportionment to out-exhaust activity (Fig. 4). The annual average of lead concentrations for two consecutive years of 1991-92 project that lead pollution trend is in increase (Fig. 5).

This city is known to be a highly industrialized city and the increased lead level may also have significant contribution due to sources other than autoemission.

The ambient lead concentration levels of Kanpur city are comparable with other metrocities of India as well as the world (Fig. 6). Kanpur city with annual average concentrations of $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ ranks 8th next to Ruhr while

recorded rangewise it is 28th in rank. The annual lead profile of Kanpur is higher than Delhi and Mumbai even though the transportation activity in Kanpur city is on considerably low profile.

Pollution control measures : Formulation of lead control strategy needs the search for the best balance between health, social benefit and environmental risk. Normally it

Fig. 5. Annual average of ambient lead in Kanpur city.

involves a process in which various environmental control strategies are evaluated against specific potential benefit for the health of the populations concerned. Determining the control strategy for lead pollution involves consideration of many issues including control technologies that are available, cost-benefit considerations and the general economic situation in the country.

(i) Control at the source is the best strategy for pollution abatement. One of the control measures involves the reduction of lead levels from petrol used in transportation.

(ii) In the use of deleaded petrol, the Government of India has introduced the supply of deleaded petrol in the metrocities of India. This is a welcome step. However, looking at the lead concentration levels, the same strategy of deleaded petrol supply should be implemented for Kanpur city also.

(iii) As it is confirmed that autoexhaust is the major contributor of lead, the autoengines should be modified to include particulate trap with high efficiency. The lead is invariably associated with fine particulates (P-10 micron size) and therefore, pollution arrest at the source will be the best strategy for abatement of lead pollution.

(iv) Disciplined traffic on the road is urgently required which will reduce traffic congestion leading to pollution build up at inhalation level.

(v) Maintenance and improving the road structure and aesthetics will also help reduce pollution levels to some extent. It is, therefore, advocated to grow trees along the road for abating the pollution from autoexhaust and other ground-level sources. Trees like *Eugenia (Jamun)* and *Nerium (Kaner)* growing along roadsides accumulate and adsorb lead from air.

Experimental

Sampling sites : A network spreaded over Kanpur city was operated activity zonewise to get entire coverage of ambient respirable suspended particulate matter (RSPM)

Fig. 6. Comparison of annual lead average of Kanpur with other of the world.

and lead. City Kanpur was selected on the basis of (i) representative of major regional group centres, (ii) high rate of industrialization and urbanization and (iii) representing the regional topoclimatic characteristics of India. In Kanpur city, three sampling sites representing residential, commercial and industrial activity zones were selected.

Sampling procedure : The samples for respirable particulate matter (RPM) were collected using high-volume samplers operated at a rate of 1.5 m³/min. RPM concentrations were determined by collecting the particulate matter for 24 h on pre-weighed glass fibre filter (20 × 25 cm) and reweighed after sampling in order to determine the mass concentration of the particles collected. The concentration of particulate matter in ambient air was then computed on the net mass collected in proportion to volume of air sampled. The details of sampling procedure are given elsewhere¹⁹.

Sample preparation : Twelve circles (1" dia) were punched out from a filter paper and put in a corning conical flask. Concentrated nitric acid (15 ml) was added to it and the conical flask was covered with a watch glass and heated at 140° in a fumehooded hot plate, until most of the acid was evaporated. This step was repeated twice in order to solubilize the metallic compounds. The solution was then filtered in another conical flask through 0.45 micron Whatman filter paper and the insoluble residue on the filter paper was rinsed with 10% nitric acid (10 ml). The bottom of the watch glass was rinsed with 10% nitric acid and the solution was evaporated to dryness. The paper blank and nitric acid blanks were then cooled and the residue was dissolved in conc. HNO₃ (1.0 ml). The clear solution was made upto 100 ml using double-distilled water. Finally the

digested samples were analyzed by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). Five replicates were taken and the average values were used for calculating the results²⁰.

Working standard solutions were aspirated into flame, and the absorbance was recorded. Appropriately diluted samples were aspirated directly into the AAS and absorbances recorded for comparison with standards. Distilled water was aspirated after each sample. A mid-range standard was also aspirated once after every 10 samples to assure the accuracy of the sample determinations. To the extent possible all determinations were based on replicate analysis. Finally the levels of lead were calculated taking an account of whole paper area and volume of the air sampled.

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References

1. "CPCB Report", Programmes objective Series : Probes/46/1992, 1992.
2. "Census of India, Final Population Totals", Paper-1 of 1992, Government of India, 1991.
3. "Hand Book of Statistics", Confederation of Indian Industry, 1992, 23-26.
4. WHO, Environmental health criteria 3, 1977, Lead, Geneva.
5. P. K. JAIN and S. MOHAN, 'Proceeding of National Seminar on Environmental Pollution Control and Monitoring', 1986.
6. C. B. PANDYA, T. S. PATEL, D. J. PARIKH, S. K. CHATTERJEE, and N. C. RAMANATHAN *J. Environ. Biol.*, 1983, 4, 127.
7. H. V. KHAN, *J. Envir. Sci. Hlth.*, 1981, A16, 637.
8. H. A. WALEED, A. MOTABERUDDIN, and M. M. KHALID, *Envir. Int.*, 1990, 16, 85.
9. D. R. BROWN, *Atmos. Environ.*, 1986, 20, 1303.
10. A. C. CHAMBERLAIN, *Atmos. Environ.*, 1983, 17, 677.
11. V. J. WATTER and E. RAVEENDRAN, *Envir. Technol.*, 1990, 11, 491.
12. R. N. KHANDEKAR, U. C. MISHRA, and K. G. VOHRA, *Sci. Total Environ.*, 1984, 40, 269.
13. A. TRIPATHI, *Atmos. Envir.*, 1994, 28, 2117.
14. D. G. GAJGHATE and M. Z. HASAN, *J. Chem. Environ. Sci.*, 1995, 4, 67.
15. A. L. AGGARWAL, D. G. GAJGHATE, R. THAKRE, and M. Z. HASAN, 'Workshop on Lead Pollution, Control and Monitoring', 1995, T16.
16. "NEERI Report : Air quality status (1991-1992)", 1991.
17. R. N. KHANDEKAR, D. N. KELKAR, and K. G. VOHRA, *Atmos. Environ.*, 1980, 14, 457.
18. "Annual Report (1955, 1976)", National Institute of Occupational Health (NIOH), Ahmedabad, 1972.
19. M. JANSSENS and R. DAMS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 65, 41.
20. D. G. GAJGHATE, "Training Manual of QA/QC on National Ambient Air Quality Monitoring", NEERI, 1995.